

ENVIRONMENT: A HUMAN RIGHT?

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ABSTRACT

With increasing exploitation of natural resource and degrading quality of the environment, the human race faces an extremely dangerous future ahead of us. The current situation shows that if nothing is done, our lives will be full of uncertainty in the future and even though we might have the basic human rights, the most essential requirement to actually enjoy those right, that is a healthy and safe environment will not exist. The authors of this article has tried to show the relation between the human right and the environment. They also have tried to show how the right to environment is related to or can be inferred from other rights such as: right to life, right to health and right to property. Along with these this paper also highlights the international treaties and statutes that deal with the protection of environment. The authors have also given reference to Indian constitutions as well as the constitutions of some other countries and discussed certain sections that deals with the environment.

Indian Journal of Contemporary
Legal and Social Issues

1. INTRODUCTION:

“The earth, the air, the land and the water are not an inheritance from our fore fathers but on loan from our children. So we have to handover to them at least as it was handed over to us.”
- Mahatma Gandhi

One of the most important things in our lives is the environment. The full enjoyment of a wide variety of human rights, such as the rights to life, health, food, water, and sanitation, requires a safe, clean, and healthy environment. We cannot achieve our goals or simply live at a level that is appropriate with human dignity unless we live in a healthy environment. Over the years mankind has developed in a fast pace however, the environment that we live in has failed to adapt to our pace and this has led to what we see now, that is an environment where sometimes it is hard for people to even find clean air to breathe. Life will cease to exist if these components such as air and water are polluted or removed or destroyed. Our life support system, that is, the environment must be maintained and preserved in order to safeguard human life. And even though we very well understand the importance of environment, over two decades have passed on with people still debating whether the right to environment is a human right or not. However, the understanding of the connection between human rights and the environment has grown significantly in recent years. International and domestic legislation, judicial rulings, and academic research on the link between human rights and the environment are fast increasing in number and breadth. The human rights and the environment mandate, which was established in March 2012 and was recently expanded, investigates human rights duties in relation to a safe, clean, healthy, and sustainable environment. It also supports best practises in the application of human rights to environmental policymaking. The right to health encompasses a wide range of things that contribute to living a healthy life. The Committee on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights, which is in charge of monitoring the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights, refers to these as "underlying determinants of health." They include, among other things, good environmental conditions.¹

Many states' constitutions now include a right to a healthy environment. However, many concerns concerning the link between human rights and the environment remain unsolved and need to be investigated further.

1.1 WHAT IS HUMAN RIGHT?

¹ *About Human Rights and Environment*, OHCHR, (May 5, 2022, 8:00AM), <https://www.ohchr.org/EN/Issues/Environment/SREnvironment/Pages/AboutHRandEnvironment.aspx> .

We as people might live in different countries and may be entitled to rights that our respective country recognises but there some rights that are given to every single one irrespective of their nationality, gender, ethnicity or social status. Such rights are known as human rights and includes the right to life and liberty, freedom from slavery and torture, freedom of opinion and expression, the right to work and education, and many more.² They are utilitarian in the sense that they apply anywhere and at all times, and they are equal in the sense that they are the same for everyone. They are viewed as involving tolerance and the rule of law, as well as having a duty on individuals to uphold the human rights of others, and they are usually regarded as not being taken away but as a condition of due process depending on particular circumstances. Human rights doctrine has had a major impact on international law and multinational and regional organisations. State and non-governmental organisation actions shape the foundation of global foreign policy. According to the definition of human rights, "if the public dialogue of peacetime global culture can be said to have a shared normative vocabulary, it is that of human rights." The theory of human rights' broad arguments appear to elicit substantial scepticism and controversy over the material, existence, and justifications of human rights to this day.

1.2 ENVIRONMENT LAW:

The collection of laws, norms, agreements, and common law governing how people interact with their environment is environmental legislation. Environmental law seeks to preserve the environment and develop regulations for the use of natural resources by individuals. In addition to protecting the environment from harm, environmental laws also decide who can utilise natural resources and under what terms and conditions. Pollution, the exploitation of natural resources, forest preservation, mineral exploitation and populations of animals and fish can be regulated by law.

Despite early precedents, the notion of "environmental law" as an unique body of law is a twentieth-century innovation. It was not until the 1960s that the natural environment was recognised as vulnerable and in need of specific legal safeguards, that this understanding was translated into legal structures, that those structures were developed into a wider body of "environmental law," and that environmental law had a considerable impact on natural resource laws. Several factors were at play at the time, including a rising understanding of the biosphere's unity and fragility, as well as heightened public concern about the impact of industrial activities on natural resources and human health. The growing regulatory state, as well as the emergence and popularity of environmentalism

² Nickel James, *Human Rights*, Stanford University (May 7,2022, 6:30 PM), <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/rights-human/>

as a political movement, converged to create a massive new body of legislation in a very short period of time. While environmental law has a tumultuous contemporary past, by the end of the twentieth century it had established itself as a part of the legal landscape in all industrialised countries, as well as many developing countries, and the greater project of international law.

2. IS ENVIRONMENT A HUMAN RIGHT?

Human rights are legal rights that have one or more of the following characteristics: appurtenance to the human person or group; necessity for international order; imperative for human life, security, survival, integrity, freedom, and equality; necessity as a position in humanity's conscience; requirement for the rights of minority groups as well as universality. All of the following features are present in the human right to the environment. Furthermore, all of the characteristics of a new generation's right are present: development of a specialised corpus of international environmental law; development of a clearly recognised international legislative procedure; integration of the right as a human right within municipal legal systems, as well as the necessity for coordinated efforts from all social actors.

In recent years there has been a significant growth in the acknowledgment of the linkages between human rights and the environment. The quantity and extent of international and domestic legislation, court decisions and academic research on the nexus between environmental and human rights are continually expanding. In its March 2012 and 2018 mandate expanding, human rights and environmental duties connect to a safe, clean, healthy, and sustainable environment. Human rights and the environmental mission³ It also supports best practises in environmental policy making with regard to the utilisation of human rights. Many countries now include in their constitutions the right to a healthy environment. However, a number of concerns about the link between human rights and the environment remain unsolved.

Human rights and environmental protection are inextricably linked; human rights cannot be realised without a safe, clean, and good environment, and environmentally sustainable governance cannot be achieved without the establishment and protection of human rights. The right to a healthy environment is inscribed in over 100 constitutions, therefore this link is becoming more widely acknowledged.

³ *Special Rapporteur on Human Rights and the Environment*, OHCHR (May 9, 2022, 10:45AM), <https://www.ohchr.org/en/Issues/environment/SREnvironment/Pages/SREnvironmentIndex.aspx>

3. ENVIRONMENTAL RIGHTS: DEFINITION

Over the years, a lot of suggestions about what should be included within the ambit of right to environment has been made. Such suggestions includes rights such as the right to not be exposed to human made contaminants that are injurious to health, right to not be subjected to extra ordinary noise⁴ etc. However, what actually constitutes the right to environment, still remains unclear. Along with this lack of clarity another parallel discussions about as to what comes under the term ‘environment’ still continues. Some basic questions in this regard are: “ what is included in the term environment?” “Does this term consists if everything in the biosphere or only only those areas where human live and interact?”

The whole global ecology is so intricately linked that strategies aimed just at protecting populated regions would be ineffective in the end. The right to the environment should encompass not only the enjoyment of clean air, water, and rich land, but also the right to life without famine and sickness caused by insufficient environmental sanitation and management." Life and health of the individual are the key reference points, but other components of the environment demand protection under the right to the environment. At the end, the main goal of the right to environment is to protect the lives and well-beings of humans, to conserve the natural ecosystem⁵ and at the same time create an obligation for everyone to protect the same not only foe the current generation but also the future ones.⁶

3.1. DEDUCING RIGHT TO ENVIRONMENT FROM OTHER AVAILABLE RIGHTS:

The emergence and existence of the human right to the environment may be traced back to various previously recognised human rights such as the right to life and the right to health.

(a) Right To Life:

Over the past few decades, rapid growth in industrialization and development has led to depletion in the quality of environment that we live in and has affected the lives of every single individual. Last few decades have seen a rise in the number of life-threatening health issues that are directly or indirectly related to the uncontrolled human interference with the environment.

4 Roberts, *The Right to a Decent Environment: Progress Along a Constitutional Avenue*, Law and the Environment 134, 148 n.39 (Baldwin & Page eds. 1970).

5 *supra* note 8.

6 *supra* note 8.

The right to the environment is rooted in the United Nations Charter, as one of the Charter's primary aims is the advancement and protection of all human rights, including the right to life. According to Article 3 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights⁷, "Everyone has the right to life, liberty, and personal security." This right is echoed in Article 6(1) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), which declares that "every human beings have an inalienable right to life."⁸The very norm of this right expects the governments to ensure the availability of a safe environment to its people.

The right to life encompasses the right to survive and well-being as well. This right should be interpreted in order to protect human life from even indirect dangers, such as environmental risks.⁹The right to life should be expanded to include an implied right to a safe and decent environment. This expansion is vital because, if this right is not adequately protected, the quality of life will deteriorate, economic growth will become slower and more expensive, and, worst of all, our planet's fundamental ability to support life may be eliminated.

(b) Right To Health:

The right to health and well-being is inextricably tied to the right to life and personal security. Although no state can ensure an individual's health, governments have an affirmative commitment to avoid from enacting policies that harm the health of their inhabitants.¹⁰ If the purpose of the right to health is to safeguard health, enforcing the right to a healthy environment is one approach to achieve so. The right to a healthy environment includes the right to be protected against environmental risks such as radioactive emission, which can have long-term health consequences.

This concept has found expression in international accords and guidelines. According to Article 12 of the 1966 United Nations Convention on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights, "measures should be taken by the covenant's parties to promote full fulfilment of the right to health, including those essential for the development of all elements of environmental hygiene." Furthermore, World Health Assembly Resolution 23.61 gave recommendations on how to achieve the best potential level of health. Among these are the "establishment of effective control

7 *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*, UNITED NATIONS, (May 15, 2022, 7:15PM), <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights> ..

8 *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights*, OHCHR, (May 16, 2022, 4:00PM) <https://www.ohchr.org/EN/ProfessionalInterest/Pages/CCPR.aspx> .

9 Melissa Thorme, *Establishing Environment as a Human Right*, 19 Denv. J. Int'l L. & Pol'y 301 (1991).

10 Thorme, *supra* note 13.

over the state of the environment as a source of health and life for present and future generations."¹¹

(c) Right To Property:

According to Article 17(1) of the Universal Declaration, "everyone has the right to hold property alone or in conjunction with others." Perhaps the definition of "property" should be broadened to encompass the common property found in the world's valuable, and sometimes non-renewable, natural resources. The planet's resources should not be regarded as the sole possession of any single country. All countries should have an inherent right to participate in their exploitation and conservation, and these rights must be used with proper consideration for the equivalent rights of others. The creation of a right to the environment will assist those who want a properly structured community in which the right to life of all, or nearly all, species is recognised, with only the rights of others limiting their ability to survive. In such a community, humans would stop being destroyers and instead become compassionate custodians with the responsibility to ensure the survival of other species within the constraints imposed by the environment's life sustaining potential and within a legal framework expanded to include interests other than those simply human.

4. INTERNATIONAL CONVENTIONS AND THEIR PROVISIONS RELATING TO ENVIRONMENT:

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The year 1972 was a milestone this aspect of environment, when United Nations Conference on the Human Environment was held at Stockholm (Sweden) from fifth to sixteenth June, in which Declaration on the Human Environment was concluded. This might be considered as the start of development of environmental rights on the planet. The Stockholm Declaration of 1972 was maybe the primary significant endeavour to moderate and ensure the human climate at the global level. The introduction of it expresses, "the need for a common outlook and for common principles to inspire and guide the peoples of the world in the preservation and enhancement of the human environment."¹²

11 Thorne, *supra* note 13.

12 Louis B. Soinn, The Stockholm Declaration on the Human Environment, 14. Harvard 430(1973)

In the UDHR, ICCPR, ICESCR there are no specific or unequivocal right mentioned regarding the quality of environment. Nonetheless the issue of environment in relation to hygiene is mentioned in the ICESCR. Article 24, paragraph 2 (c) of CRC expects States to seek information about the highest attainable standard of wellbeing mulling over the threats and dangers of ecological contamination. The World Commission for Environment and Development defined “sustainable development” as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. It contains within it two key concepts: the concept of 'needs', in particular the essential needs of the world's poor, to which overriding priority should be given; and the idea of limitations imposed by the state of technology and social organization on the environment's ability to meet present and future needs.”

UN Human Rights Committee has embraced different General Comments that are pertinent to climate and environment prominently General Remarks 14 and 15, which decipher Articles 11 and 12 of the ICESCR to incorporate safe, adequate, and moderate quantity of water for purposes of sterilization, daily use and to conserve water future generations. The UN 6th committee commentary on the Watercourses Convention indicates that “In determining 'vital human needs' special attention is to be paid to providing sufficient water to sustain human life, including both drinking water and water required for the production of food in order to prevent starvation.”¹³

The Right to Decent Living Conditions Article 25 of the UDHR recognizes the right to an adequate standard of living, stating that: “(1) Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and his family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond his control. (2) Motherhood and childhood are entitled to special care and assistance. All Children, whether born in or out of wedlock shall enjoy the same social protection.”

The Right to a Healthy Environment ICESCR in article 12(2) on the right to health states that “The steps to be taken by the States Parties to the present Covenant to achieve the full realization of this right shall include those necessary for . . . (b) The improvement of all aspects of environmental and industrial hygiene”. In terms of environmental responsibility, a few agreements and accords with

13 Rept. of the 6th Committee Working Group, GAOR A/51/869 (1997)

potentially worldwide application are: The Vienna Convention of 1985 established a framework within which nations can collaborate to address the problem of ozone depletion. The signing countries pledged to take "appropriate measures . . . to protect human health and the environment against adverse effects resulting or likely to result from human activities which modify or are likely to modify the ozone layer according to the international ozone commission"

Since 1972, an increasing number of constitutions have included some form of environmental legislation. However, some obviously make no connections between environmental rights and any form of human rights. Article 37 of the European Union's Charter of Fundamental Rights, for example, simply states that "A high level of environmental protection and the improvement of the quality of the environment must be integrated into the policies of the Union and ensured in accordance with the principle of sustainable development."¹⁴

5. INDIAN LAWS RELATING TO ENVIRONMENT.

The Indian constitution is the largest written constitution that evolves over time and the environmental provisions are a result of the evolving characteristic of the constitution. The Environment (Protection) Act, 1986 defines environment as "environment includes water, air and land and the interrelationship which exists among and between air, water and land and human beings, other living creatures, plants, micro-organism and property". India being a welfare and democratic state there are constitutional mandates which aim to secure and improve the environment. The fundamental rights in part 3 and directive principles in part 4 of the Indian constitution incorporate several articles and provisions regarding the protection of the environment.

Indian Constitution forces an obligation on each resident to secure climate and environment. Article 51-A (g), says that it is an obligation of each resident of India to secure and improve the natural, indigenous habitat including woods, lakes, waterways and untamed life and to have empathy for living animals. Article 48 mentions association of farming and animal cultivation. It also guides the State to find ways to arrange horticulture and creature cultivation on present day logical lines. Article

¹⁴ Promoting and protecting your fundamental rights according to the EU, European agency of fundamental rights, (May 30, 2022, 5:15AM) (<https://fra.europa.eu/>)

48 -A of the constitution also mentions that the state shall work to protect and improve the environment and to safeguard the forests and wild life of the country.

As per Article 21 of the constitution no individual will be denied liberty except when indicated by system set up by law. The Supreme Court in *Maneka Gandhi versus Association of India*, (AIR 1978 SC 597)[5] ensured that right to life, Right to climate and environment liberated from risk of sickness and disease is characteristic in it. Right to clean environment is vital to live with dignity.

6. OTHER CONSTITUTIONS INCORPORATING ENVIRONMENTAL PROVISIONS.

Some constitutions take their cues from Article 12 of the 1966 United Nations Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights. Thus, Article 35 of the Republic of Korea's Constitution provides that "all people should have the right to a healthy and pleasant environment," but then goes on to add that the substance of this right should be decided by law.

Other constitutions place a greater emphasis on human rights in the environment. Article 45 of the Spanish Constitution declares that everyone has "the right to enjoy an environment suitable for the development of the person as well as the duty to preserve it." It then directs public authorities to concern themselves with "the rational use of all natural resources for the purpose of protecting and improving the quality of life and protecting and restoring the environment...."

Article 56 of the Turkish Constitution is similar: "Everyone has the right to live in a healthy, balanced environment. It shall be the duty of the State and the citizens to improve and preserve the environment and to prevent environmental pollution according to ref world"

Article 42 of the 1993 Russian Constitution states that "the right to a favorable environment, reliable information about its condition and to compensation for the damage caused to his or her health or property by ecological violations."¹⁵

15 Russian.CONST. art. XLII, pt. II

The 1996 South African Constitution states “to an environment that is not harmful to their health or well-being; and to have the environment protected, for the benefit of present and future generations, through reasonable legislative and other measures that prevent pollution and ecological degradation; promote conservation; and secure ecologically sustainable development and use of natural resources while promoting justifiable economic and social development.”¹⁶

7. CONCLUSION:

Articulating a right to a climate, environment suitable to living beings inside the setting of social rights isn't innately risky. Explaining the presence of a right would involve giving more prominent load to the worldwide public interest in ensuring protection of the environment and advancing reasonable turn of events, yet this could be accomplished without harming the basic structure texture of laws relating to human rights, and in a way which completely regards the wide edge of appreciation that states are qualified for practice when determining financial, natural, and social strategy goals. It would expand on existing points of reference under the ICESCR, and ponder global approach practical advancement supported at Rio in 1992 and in resulting worldwide gatherings.

The further elaboration of procedural rights, in view of the Aarhus Show, would work with the execution of a right, and give more importance universally to the job of NGOs openly interested in litigation and prosecution. These two improvements go inseparably. They are not a fundamental piece of any presentation or convention on basic liberties or environment and human rights, yet they do address an intelligent augmentation of existing strategies and would address a genuine exercise in reformist advancement of the law. Current issues relating to the environment require new methodologies to tackle them. The human rights connected to ecological needs is an affirmation that protection to the environment won't be effective without human interference. A scope of different activities are needed at both the national and global level, with basic human rights giving the premise to such activity.

16 South African. CONST. art. X, pt. IV.